

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

医中誌 Web

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

100 件強のため、会議録除外、animals 除外はしていません

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      @"Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"/TH 4,895
2      "ガンマ-アミノ酪酸"/TA or "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"/TA or "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"/TA or ガンマアミノ酪酸/TA or ガンマロ
ン/TA or "ギャバ"/TA or "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or "γ-アミノブチル酸"/TA or "γ-アミノ酪酸"/TA or "γアミノ酪酸"/TA or

```


"gamma Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or "Gammalon"/TA or "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"/TA or Aminoalor/TA or アミノロン/TA or GABA/TA 7,933			
3	#1 OR #2	9,121	
4	(交感神経系/TH and 副交感神経系/TH) AND 活性/TA	87	
5	副交感神経系/TA and 活性/TA	62	
6	(クロモグラニン A/TA or "Chromogranin A"/TA or "Chromogranin A"/TH) or ("CgA"/TA and 疲労/TA)	2,665	
7	"心理的ストレス"/TH	55,246	
8	心理的ストレス/TA or 精神的ストレス/TA or "Psychologic Stress"/TA or "Psychological Stress"/TA or メンタルストレス/TA or 心的ストレス/TA or 心理ストレス/TA or 心理的負担/TA or 精神的負担/TA or "Emotional Stress"/TA or "Emotional Distress"/TA or "Mental Suffering"/TA	6,084	
9	精神性/TA and 疲労/TA	10	
10	(リラクゼーション/TA or リラクゼーション/TA or リラックス/TA)	4,246	
11	relaxation/TA	1,084	
12	"リラクゼーション"/TH	6,570	
13	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12	68,814	
14	#3 AND #13	105	

Key articles: 2015386123 OR 2010058176 OR 2008134199 OR 2019230880 OR 2008239909 OR 2012013033

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/7/30

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

#4, #5 : 活性/TA の掛け合わせは外しても OK
#6 : ("CgA"/TA and 疲労/TA) →このままでもよいですが、GABA と掛け合わせるので” and 疲労/TA”は外しても OK
#7 : @ストレス/TH も加えてはいかがでしょうか
#9 : 睡眠は除外とのことで疲労と精神性を掛け合わせで工夫されたのかと思いますが、気分なども対象にしてよいならば、広めに
“疲労/TH OR 唾液/TH”なども加えてはいかがでしょうか
絞込 : 結果が 100 件越えの場合、血压と同様、not ((CK=動物) not (CK=ヒト))、会議録除くの 2つの絞込みもご検討ください。
※2021342552, 2019308886, 2017175774

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/10

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

MEDLINE

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

PubMed

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

"stress reducing"[tiab::~0] OR "stress reduce"[tiab::~0] OR "mental stress"[tiab] OR "reduces anxiety"[tiab::~0] OR "reduce anxiety"[tiab::~0] OR relaxation*[Title/Abstract] OR "psychological stress"[tiab::~1] 160,877 だと (relaxation で拾われた文献で)ノイズが結構多かったので#6 に修正.
 CgA[tiab] AND ("stress reduce"[tiab::~2] OR "stress reducing"[tiab::~2]) //~1 と~2 の差分を比較し 19757975 を拾っていたので~2 にしました

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	"gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Mesh:NoExp]	40,369
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2 "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR Ainalon*[Title/Abstract] OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR Gammalon[Title/Abstract] OR GABA[tiab] OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract] OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"[Title/Abstract:~0] 69,510

3 #1 OR #2 81,873

4 "Stress, Psychological"[mh] 152,699

5 "Relaxation"[Mesh] 21,827

6 "Psychological Stressor"[tiab] OR "Psychological Stressors"[tiab] OR "stress reducing"[tiab:~0] OR "stress reduce"[tiab:~0] OR "mental stress"[tiab] OR "reduces anxiety"[tiab:~0] OR "reduce anxiety"[tiab:~0] OR (relaxation*[tiab] AND stress*[tiab]) OR "psychological stress"[tiab:~1] 35,618

7 "Chromogranin A"[Mesh] 3,418

8 "ChromograninA"[tiab] OR "Chromogranin A"[tiab] 5,751

9 CgA[tiab] AND ("stress reduce"[tiab:~2] OR "stress reducing"[tiab:~2]) 10

10 #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 204,382

11 #3 AND #7 973

12 ("Animals"[MeSH] NOT (Animals[MeSH] AND "Humans"[MeSH])) 5,135,051

13 #8 NOT #9 342

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/8/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

コメントいただいた#6, #9 の調整、確認しました。ありがとうございます。
件数がやや多めのため、#4 "Stress, Psychological"[mh], #5"Relaxation"[Mesh]は Mesh Major Topic としてもよいかもしれませんが、漏れる可能性もありお任せします。90 件程しか減りませんが、GABA 受容体の文献がある程度落ちると思います。key articles4 件は含まれます。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/11

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Willey)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      MeSH descriptor: [gamma-Aminobutyric Acid] this term only in Cochrane Reviews          30
2      ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR
GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane
Reviews in Cochrane Reviews          42
3      #1 OR #2 in Cochrane Reviews          42
4      MeSH descriptor: [Relaxation] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews          5

```


5	MeSH descriptor: [Stress, Psychological] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	34,643
6	MeSH descriptor: [Chromogranin A] explode all trees in Cochrane Reviews	0
7	(Psychological NEXT Stressor* OR stress NEAR/2 reduc* OR "mental stress" OR reduce* NEAR/1 anxiety OR (relaxation* AND stress*) OR psychological NEAR/2 stress):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	157
8	("ChromograninA" OR "Chromogranin A"):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
9	("CgA" AND (stress NEAR/2 reduc*)):ti,ab,kw in Cochrane Reviews	0
10	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 in Cochrane Reviews	165
11	#3 AND #10 in Cochrane Reviews	1

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340(PubMed)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
---------	--------------	-----------------------	----------------------

1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。ありがとうございます。
#7は、NEAR/1→2 (CENTRALと同様)としてもよいと思います。(結果件数に影響なし)

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/11

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

The Cochrane Library(Wiley)

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

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Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

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Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

1      MeSH descriptor: [gamma-Aminobutyric Acid] this term only in Trials      1393
2      ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR
GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"):ti,ab,kw in Trials in
Trials      3487
3      #1 OR #2 in Trials      3487

```


4	MeSH descriptor: [Relaxation] explode all trees in Trials	2353
5	MeSH descriptor: [Stress, Psychological] explode all trees in Trials	7893
6	MeSH descriptor: [Chromogranin A] explode all trees in Trials	45
7	(Psychological NEXT Stressor* OR stress NEAR/2 reduc* OR "mental stress" OR reduce* NEAR/2 anxiety OR (relaxation* AND stress*) OR psychological NEAR/2 stress):ti,ab,kw in Trials	20982
8	("ChromograninA" OR "Chromogranin A"):ti,ab,kw in Trials	181
9	("CgA" AND (stress NEAR/2 reduc*)):ti,ab,kw in Trials	4
10	#4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 in Trials	24010
11	#3 AND #10 in Trials	76

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340(Pubmed) CENTRAL は 19462324 OR 22203366 がインデックスされている

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/8/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。ありがとうございます。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/12

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

CINAHL with Full Text

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

血圧の時より広めに拾っています S2

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

```

S1      (MH "GABA")    Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase      2,648
S2      TX "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR
GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" Expanders - Apply
equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 9,051
S3      S1 OR S2      9,051
S4      (MH "Stress, Physiological+")    Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 5,570

```


S5 (MH "Relaxation") Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 5,573
S6 TI (Psychological W0 Stressor* OR stress N0 reduc* OR "mental stress" OR reduce* N0 anxiety OR (relaxation* AND stress*) OR psychologic* W0 stress) OR AB (Psychological W0 Stressor* OR stress N0 reduc* OR "mental stress" OR reduce* N0 anxiety OR (relaxation* AND stress*) OR psychologic* W0 stress) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 13,679
S7 TI ("ChromograninA" OR "Chromogranin A") OR AB ("ChromograninA" OR "Chromogranin A") Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 428
S8 TI ("CgA" AND (stress N0 reduc*)) OR AB ("CgA" AND (stress N0 reduc*)) Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 1
S9 S4 OR S5 OR S6 OR S7 OR S8 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 24,471
S10 S3 AND S9 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Boolean/Phrase 95

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340(CINAHL には含まれない)

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

S4 ですが、Pubmed と共通の (MH "Stress, Psychological+") の方を使用してはいかがでしょうか。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/20

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

African Index Medicus, Index Medicus for the Eastern Mediterranean Region, Index Medicus for the South-East Asia Region, Latin America and the Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences, Western Pacific Region Index Medicus

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Global Index Medicus

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1 (tw:("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR aminalon* OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR gammalon OR gaba OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid" OR "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid") OR (mh:("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"))) AND (tw:("Psychological Stressor" OR "Psychological Stressors" OR "stress reducing" OR "stress reduce" OR

"mental stress" OR "reduces anxiety" OR "reduce anxiety" OR "psychological stress") OR (mh:("Stress, Psychological" OR "Relaxation")) 17

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/13

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。ありがとうございます。
Relaxation も *tw* に追加すると (29 件)、必要なものというよりはノイズが増えた (他の成分による筋弛緩の作用など) ため、このままでよいように思います。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/19

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICOs, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

履歴の組み合わせ機能なし

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1 in the Title (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") 153 records for 152 trials found!

2 in the Intervention (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") 90 records for 78 trials found

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions

- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。ありがとうございます。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/19

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

血圧と同じ。 (outcome を検索に含めていない。 Outcome を指定する機能がない) 履歴の組み合わせ機能なし

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	MeSH DESCRIPTOR gamma-Aminobutyric Acid EXPLODE ALL TREES	67
2	"gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" 46 // " フレーズなしでも 46	
3	Aminalon 1	
4	"4-Aminobutanoic Acid" 0 // " フレーズなしでも 0	

5	"4-Aminobutyric Acid"	2
6	Gammalon	0
7	GABA	180
8	"γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0
9	"γ-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
10	"Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。
※free term 検索で 203 件

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/20

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

ClinicalTrials.gov (classic)

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., **P**atient, **I**ntervention, **C**omparison, **O**utcome, and **S**tudy Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Aminalton OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("psychological stress")
1

2 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("stress reduce") 0

3 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("stress reducing") 0

4 " Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("mental stress") 1

5 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Relaxation") 71

6 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("reduce anxiety") 12

7 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("reducing anxiety ") 15

8 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("Chromogranin A") 0

9 Other terms (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND ("ChromograninA") 0

10 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND Outcome Measures ("stress") 36

11 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND Outcome Measures ("Relaxation") 25

12 Intervention/treatment (Recruitment status:ALL) ("gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Ainalon OR "4-Aminobutanoic Acid" OR "4-Aminobutyric Acid" OR Gammalon OR GABA OR "γ-Amino Butyric Acid" OR "γ-Aminobutyric Acid") AND Outcome Measures ("Chromogranin A") 0

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/13

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested

C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were "revision required," this response must be "revisions required.").

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

確認しました。ありがとうございます。組み合わせは十分だと思います。

Table 10: PRESS Guideline — Search Submission and Peer Review Assessment

Search Submission: This section is to be filled in by the searcher

Searcher: 社外協力者 D

Email: (非開示)

Date submitted: 2023/07/20

Date requested by: Click or tap here to enter text.

Search Topic or Title:

Effect of GABA intake on stress

This search strategy is:

My PRIMARY (core) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

This search strategy is:

My SECONDARY (supplemental) database strategy:

This is my first submission

This is submitted after feedback

Database(s)

(e.g., MEDLINE, CINAHL, Embase): **[mandatory]**

UMIN-CTR

Database Platform(s)

(e.g., Ovid, EBSCO): **[mandatory]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

*If your chosen database or platform provides a link to the search history, please provide it here:

Research Question(s)

(Describe the purpose of the search) **[mandatory]**

Does taking GABA affect stress?

PICO(S) or Related Format

(Outline the PICO, SPIDER, PEPSI, etc. for your question — i.e., Patient, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Study Design — as applicable)

- P** Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.
- I** *GABA*
- C** Click or tap here to enter text.
- O** Stress (Psychological)
- S** Click or tap here to enter text.

Inclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as age groups, study designs, and so on to be included) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Exclusion Criteria

(List criteria such as study designs, date limits, and so on to be excluded) [optional]

Click or tap here to enter text.

Were Search Filters Applied? [mandatory]

- Yes
- No

If YES, which were used (e.g., Cochrane RCT filter, CADTH's Guidelines filter, PubMed Clinical Queries filter)? Provide the source if this is a published filter. **[mandatory if the answer was YES]**

Enter any content that you want to repeat, including other content controls. You can also insert this control around table rows in order to repeat parts of a table.

Other notes or comments you feel would be useful for the peer reviewer (e.g., decision on date or language limits, articles used in pulling search terms)? **[optional]**

UMIN-CTR は掛け合わせ機能がないため、GABA 関連語のみで検索 (血圧と同じです)

Copy and paste your search strategy here, exactly as run, including the number of hits per line. **[mandatory]**

1	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0	//” ” フレーズなしでも 0
2	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Ainalon	0	
3	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"	0	
4	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "4-Aminobutyric Acid"	0	

5	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード Gammalon	0
6	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0
7	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
8	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
9	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマ-アミノ酪酸	0
10	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマアミノ酪酸	0
11	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ガンマロン	0
12	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード ギャバ	3
13	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γ-アミノブチル酸	0
14	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γ-アミノ酪酸	22
15	フリーワード検索：検索キーワード γアミノ酪酸	0
16	検索：目的1 "gamma-Aminobutyric Acid" 0//16-23 は本番では省略もありかと考えます (ご意見お願いします)	
17	検索：目的1 Aminalon 0	
18	検索：目的1 "4-Aminobutanoic Acid"	0
19	検索：目的1 "4-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
20	検索：目的1 Gammalon	0
21	検索：目的1 "γ-Amino Butyric Acid"	0
22	検索：目的1 "γ-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
23	検索：目的1 "Hydrochloride gamma-Aminobutyric Acid"	0
24	検索：目的1 ガンマ-アミノ酪酸	0
25	検索：目的1 ガンマアミノ酪酸	0
26	検索：目的1 ガンマロン	0
27	検索：目的1 ギャバ	0
28	検索：目的1 γ-アミノブチル酸	0
29	検索：目的1 γ-アミノ酪酸	2
30	検索：目的1 γアミノ酪酸	0

Key articles: 19462324 OR 16971751 OR 22203366 OR 30972340

Peer Review Assessment: This section is to be filled in by the reviewer

Reviewer: 社外協力者 E

Email: (非開示)

Date completed: 2023/08/12

1. Translation of Research Question(s)

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

[Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

2. Boolean and Proximity Operators

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

3. Subject Headings

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

4. Text Word Searching

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

5. Spelling, Syntax, and Line Numbers

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Click or tap here to enter text.

6. Limits and Filters

- A) No revisions
- B) Revision(s) suggested
- C) Revision(s) required

If "B" or "C," please provide an explanation or example:

Overall Evaluation (Note: If 1 or more of the previous elements were “revision required,” this response must be “revisions required.”).

- A) No revisions
 B) Revision(s) suggested
 C) Revision(s) required

Additional Comments (including sources of additional search terms, such as the use of text mining software or resources such as ChemID):

Click or tap here to enter text.

Please select the most appropriate answer for each element.

Element	No revisions	Revision(s) suggested	Revision(s) required
1. Translation of research question	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Boolean and proximity operators	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Subject headings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Text word searching	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Spelling, syntax, and line numbers	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Limits and filters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall evaluation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If revisions are suggested or required, please provide an explanation or example:

title 検索ではほぼ網羅していると思うので、目的1の検索は日本語の表記のみに省略してさしつかえないと思います。